

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for African and European **Digital Innovation Hubs.**

6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan – Second version

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Glossary and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CSO	Civil Society Organization
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
EU	European Union
HPC	High- performance Computing
ICT	Information, Communication & Technology
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
MS	Microsoft
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SMEs	Small – Medium Enterprises

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Executive Summary

This document aims to provide the AfriConEU consortium with an effective and efficient plan to follow in communicating and disseminating the work and results of the project. A separate document will describe how the exploitation of the results will be achieved (D6.14 and D6.15). This is the second version of the communication and dissemination plan and includes some parts from the first version with updates and additions on the strategy that was submitted in version 1 in M3 (D6.1). The upcoming versions (D6.3 and D6.4) will update the strategy and report on all the implemented dissemination and communication activities, including their effectiveness in reaching the established goals.

The initial plan for communication and dissemination actions was designed at the beginning of the project, in March 2021 (Month 3 – D6.1). This second version is delivered in February 2022 (Month 13 – D6.2) and subsequent and updated versions will be produced in May 2023 (Month 28 – D6.3), and January 2024 (Month 36 – D6.4). The more the project proceeds, the more specific and complete this document will become. This second version of the plan presents the results of initial communication and dissemination activities, as well as includes additional information, as follows:

- Description of Social Media Campaigns;
- Statistics on Social Media;
- New sections added to the website, including *Job Opportunities*, *Training Resources* and *Events*;
- Numbers achieved in Year 1;
- Table of Events for 2022;
- Tables with Planning of activities for M7-M24 in what concerns the development of communication tools and the production of deliverables within WP6.

Finally, this document is dedicated to the project's external communication. For the consortium's internal communication, the deliverable **D1.1 Management and Quality Plan** can be consulted.

1. Introduction

1.1 About AfriConEU: Distinctive traits

AfriConEU is a European project that supports the strengthening of existing Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) in Africa. It facilitates the collaboration between EU and African DIHs to strengthen a joint EU-Africa innovation and start-up ecosystem.

What makes AfriConEU different from other relevant projects?

- AfriConEU will create the first Trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European DIHs involving diverse partners and stakeholders from various industries.
- All the involved actors have unique competencies, experiences, and expertise from both continents, including Digital Innovation/Tech hubs, Universities, Consultancies, Investment firms, Civil Society Organizations (CSOs).
- This collaboration between African and European partners will empower DIHs at a local, national, continental, and trans-continental level and boost the digital economy.
- The project strengthens the EU-Africa partnership and shared agenda, reinforcing long-term collaboration with mutual benefits.

These novel and distinctive propositions have been considered to create a straightforward and standard narrative that can be used consistently throughout the project and adapted to different audiences. Part of that narrative is conveyed through the project's claim by creating the first Trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European DIHs.

1.2 Target audiences and key messages

As described in D6.1, the **primary target groups of AfriConEU** include Digital Innovation Hubs, Tech Hubs, Business Incubator Networks, Co-working Spaces, Accelerators, Local entrepreneurial and Start-up community supporters, Entrepreneurs, Digital entrepreneurs, SMEs, Young innovators, ICT professionals, Investors, Corporates, Mentors, African Diaspora Communities, Business angels, Venture funds and Foundations (Table 1). In addition, **the secondary target groups** include Pan-African Networks of innovation stakeholders, Public officers/Policy stakeholders (incl. EU & AU), Local governments, Education and training

organizations, and the General public (Table 2).

Table 1 - List of AfriConEU Primary Target Groups

Primary Target group	Goal	Website	Press Releases	Newsletter	Facebook	LinkedIn	Twitter	Instagram	YouTube
DIHs and ecosystem builders from both continents	Capacity Building and networking by enlarging their network, allowing the project to get deeper into local ecosystems, and providing them with a Pan-African/ European reach; these will also be key stakeholders to learn how to replicate AfriConEU Academy program in the future; to attract them to enrol in the platform of DIHs to be part of this network								
Tech hubs									
Business incubator networks									
Co-working spaces									
Accelerators									
Local entrepreneurial and Start-up community supporter									
Entrepreneurs	International networking opportunities; better access to investors; and a more enforced innovation ecosystem. The Consortium aims to establish AfriConEU Community of Practice as a reference for entrepreneurs/ start-ups when looking for support to internationalize, scale up, or find talents to hire; to involve them to be part of the Academy Network to gain knowledge, develop synergies, etc.								
Digital entrepreneurs									
Start-ups									
Digital start-ups									
SMEs									
Young Innovators									
ICT professionals									
Investors	To exploit the most innovative technologies and business opportunities in Africa through investment and/or partnerships; They are expected to support the project by participating in the project activities and through eventual sponsorship enabling the sustainability of the academy's programs.								
Corporates									
Mentors									
African Diaspora Communities									
Business angels									
Venture funds									
Foundations									

Table 2 - List of AfriConEU Secondary Target Groups

Secondary Target group	Goal	Website	Press Releases	Newsletters	Facebook	LinkedIn	Twitter	Instagram	YouTube
Pan-African Networks of innovation stakeholders	To engage them in the project and disseminate into their networks; to attract them for current and future collaboration.								
Public officers/ Policy stakeholders (incl. EU & AU)									
Local governments									
Education and training organizations									
General public	Follow and share; spread the word and raise awareness.								

The target groups' successful engagement is crucial to the overall project's success and, most importantly, for building a robust EU-Africa Innovation and startup ecosystem. To this end, engaging with target groups means:

- Encouraging, facilitating, and supporting the participation of relevant stakeholders in AfriConEU Academy activities (locally implemented workshops, webinars, brokerage events, design thinking boot camps, masterclasses, and project-relevant training and networking activities);
- Motivating stakeholders to contribute to the project's activities through their experience, expertise, knowledge. They will provide meaningful input to project processes and outcomes (e.g., through the research activities, the co-design of the Academy programs, and the evaluation tasks);
- Allowing stakeholders to benefit from and use the project outcomes.

The communication and dissemination strategy has been oriented not only towards the target groups but especially towards the project's *momentum*, being continuously adapted and updated, as follows:

Step 1: Raising awareness about AfriConEU and inviting the community to participate in meaningful public discussions;

Step 2: Consolidating information about the AfriConEU networking academy;

Step 3: Inviting DIHs, SMEs, entrepreneurs to participate in the capacity building;

Step 4: Decisive and timely communication about demonstration actions and capacity building experience;

Step 5: Communication for the future of AfriConEU.

In its essence, communication is a continuous process started at the beginning of the project, involving showcasing the project's activities, outcomes, intermediate and final results. Dissemination is a crucial element of the project's visibility and sustainability as well.

2. Strategy, channels, and tools

2.1 Strategy Outline

AfriConEU's communication and dissemination activities are regarded not only as a way of informing society and stakeholders about the project but also to support its development.

Three main objectives were defined since the inception of the project:

- To raise the project's awareness among digital innovation-related stakeholders in the project's nine countries and other locations around Europe and Africa, supporting the work in other WPs.
- To share experiences and results - especially on the impact of the networking academy on the beneficiaries around Europe and Africa.
- To disseminate the respective project outcomes to the broadest possible community of potential beneficiaries.

As mentioned, the consortium has been implementing the communication and dissemination strategy from the offset of the project, with actions carried out concerning the two initial phases of evolution as presented next.

2.1.1 Preparation (M1-4) - Completed

In this phase, preparation for the smooth implementation of the communication and dissemination activities took place. The project's website was created, along with the visual identity, the social media channels, and the project's communication and dissemination toolkit. Different audiences were identified and characterized to target the communication and dissemination efforts better. Templates for reporting on essential contacts and events or other dissemination activities undertaken by the partners were also created.

2.1.2 Communication: raising the awareness of the AfriConEU project (M2-36) - On-going

Once the visuals and the strategic plan were ready, the communication started by promoting the project's most significant aspects, such as the vision, objectives, name explanation, and

the partners. The information is continuously being communicated to the target audiences and the stakeholders at a regional, national and trans-continental level - special attention is being given to DIH and relevant networks. A separate communication strategy was created and is being implemented to ensure smooth synergies with relevant projects, networks, and initiatives in the Digital Innovation Hub ecosystem. The channels and tools primarily being used include the website, leaflet, social media, letterhead, pitch deck, press release, newsletter, synergies with other networks and projects, traditional media, and presentation of the third-party project events.

2.1.3 Dissemination: promoting project results among stakeholders (M3-36) - On-going

The objective is to promote results among selected stakeholders to support the adoption of the AfriConEU Logic model, relying heavily on the partner's existing wide networks. The channels and tools primarily used include event attendance, several social media campaign strategies to target, partners' networks, third-party events, and own events. Additionally, the project targets Digital Innovation conferences focusing on Entrepreneurship, Innovation, and Technology. Also, the project plans the production of scientific publications in peer-reviewed conferences and journals.

2.1.4 Exploitation and Sustainability (M23-36) – Not started yet

A dedicated exploitation and sustainability plan will be prepared and made available to the partners as a separate document by Month 25 (February 2023, D6.14) and then updated by Month 36 (January 2024, D6.15).

2.2 Communication Channels and Tools

2.2.1 Logo

The AfriConEU logo was created using the project acronym (Figure 1). The creation process

and justification of selected colours were explained in D6.1. The logo is present and included in all documents and resources produced by the consortium.

Figure 1 - AfriConEU Logo

2.2.2 AfriConEU Pitch Deck

The pitch deck developed at a early stage of the project (Figure 2) has been used by partners to present the project at several events, conferences, meetings, and other occasions.

Figure 2 - AfriConEU Pitch Deck Slides' Sample

2.2.3 AfriConEU PowerPoint Template

The AfriConEU PowerPoint template (Figure 3) is being used to create relevant presentations during the project’s participation in events, conferences, meetings, and other occasions to disseminate project developments and results, enhancing the overall dissemination efforts.

Figure 3 - AfriConEU Presentation Template

2.2.4 Word Deliverable Template

The AfriConEU deliverable template was produced in line with the overall communication and dissemination material visual identity (Figure 4). The consortium partners are using it for the development of all project deliverables.

Figure 4 - AfriConEU Word Deliverable Template

2.2.5 Website

A web page is available at <https://africoneu.eu/> since Month 2 of the project – March 2021. It intends to be the main point of information for anybody interested in the project. This is where up-to-date information about the project and its activities is published, job opportunities, events along with deliverables.

Figure 5 - AfriConEU website Home Page

The initial structure of the website is presented in D6.1. Below, the recent updated sections and changes performed are presented.

Join Section: This section includes a call for visitors to join AfriConEU depending on the category they belong to (Figure 6). It includes five sub-tabs:

1. **AfriConEU Community of Practice:** Aiming to create a vibrant online community between DIHs and innovation stakeholders from both continents.
2. **For Individuals:** Inviting people to be part of the AfriConEU Community of Practice and have access to various opportunities for training and funding.
3. **For Entities:** Inviting them to share opportunities, job offers, training seminars, and events.
4. **Events:** Including a repository with upcoming opportunities such as events, conferences, training seminars, and webinars relevant for digital innovation hubs, entrepreneurs, tech-hubs, and startups in both Africa and Europe.
5. **Job Opportunities:** Includes job offers in Europe and Africa.

Figure 6 - AfriConEU Website Join Page

Library: This section includes a gallery, scientific publications, training resources, the public deliverables of AfriConEU, and Relevant Initiatives. (Figure 7). The section of training resources includes three main categories of resources: Online Courses, Webinars, and Material. The Relevant Initiatives section includes projects related to AfriConEU: [DIGILOGIC](#), [Enrich in Africa](#), [Hubiquitous](#), [AEDIB](#), [D4D Hub](#).

Figure 7 - AfriConEU Website Library Page

Figure 8 presents performance statistics for the website of AfriConEU, gathered by Google Analytics, including number of users, number of sessions per user, total sessions, total page views, average session duration and bounce rate percentage. According to the numbers,

during the first year of the project (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022), AfriConEU website had a total of 2.431 users¹, 8.977 pageviews², an average session³ duration of about 2 minutes and 34 seconds, and a bounce rate⁴ of 52,59% indicating that almost half of the users visited more than one page in AfriConEU website.

Figure 8 - AfriConEU Website Statistics Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

Figure 9 reveals that most of the users visit AfriConEU website through desktop, while Figure 10 shows the users' geographical provenience. According to the statistics, approximately 46% of the users come from Europe, 23% from America continent, 17% from Africa, and 14% from Asia.

¹ Number of persons that have visited the website.

² "A pageview (or pageview hit, page tracking hit) is an instance of a page being loaded (or reloaded) in a browser. Pageviews is a metric defined as the total number of pages viewed." (Google Analytics Glossary, consulted on 28 February 2022. URL: https://support.google.com/analytics/answer/6086080?hl=en&ref_topic=6083659)

³ "The period of time a user is active on your site or app. By default, if a user is inactive for 30 minutes or more, any future activity is attributed to a new session. Users that leave your site and return within 30 minutes are counted as part of the original session." (Google Analytics Glossary, consulted on 28 February 2022. URL: <https://support.google.com/analytics/answer/6086069?hl=en>)

⁴ "A bounce is a single-page session on your site. (...) Bounce rate is single-page sessions divided by all sessions, or the percentage of all sessions on your site in which users viewed only a single page and triggered only a single request to the Analytics server." (Google Analytics Tips, consulted on 28 February 2022. URL: <https://support.google.com/analytics/answer/1009409?hl=en>)

Figure 9 - AfriConEU Website Statistics Year 1 – Devices

Figure 10 - AfriConEU Website Statistics Year 1 – Countries

2.2.6 Social Media

AfriConEU aims to have a strong presence in social media, enhancing its reach-out to target audiences and the general public. The project has established, in March 2021 (M2), social media accounts for Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, and a YouTube Channel. All channels are monitored regularly, and changes are made according to the audience’s engagement and feedback. The project’s identifier hashtag is **#AfriConEU**, accompanied by the secondary hashtags **#DIH**, **#H2020**, **#EUAfrica** and **#AfricaEurope** when needed. The number and type of hashtags change depending on the specific social media. The project has a [Linktree account](https://linktr.ee/africoneu)⁵, including the social media accounts and a subscription form link to the Newsletter. The Linktree includes buttons and links promoting project-related events and opportunities.

⁵ <https://linktr.ee/africoneu>

2.2.6.1 Social media management tool

A social media management tool is being used to better strategize and execute the social media plan. Through this tool – all social media accounts and pages are managed, with the possibility of customizing each channel with different information and material. It provides all the needed tools in one platform, and some of the significant features include Publishing & Scheduling (Figure 11 & 12) , Interactions or Engagement, Content Creation & Media Library, Social Listening & Monitoring, Reporting & Analytics, and Team Collaboration. The tool provides instant access to brand mentions across social, news, blogs, forums, reviews, while it helps the project understand how its brand makes people really feel about sentiment analysis (positive, negative & neutral). It helps uncover trends and conversations of any keywords, hashtags, and phrases across the web. The AfriConEU social media plan is being executed through the Publishing & Scheduling , in which the social media management team can cross-check social publish, edit, and filter, complete post customization per channel, while composing a new post.

Figure 11 – Eclincher Publishing Calendar: detailed view

Figure 12 – Eclinch Publishing Calendar: summary view

2.2.6.2 Social media monthly analytics report

At the end of each month, the consortium receives a detailed analytics report from YMH about all the social media accounts, which helps drive strategic decisions for improving the project’s social media performance.

2.2.6.3 Facebook page

The AfriConEU Facebook page⁶ serves primarily for communication with the general public (Figure 13). Secondly, it also communicates to local entrepreneurial and start-up community supporters, entrepreneurs, young innovators, ICT professionals, mentors, and African diaspora communities. Two to three posts per week are published on the Facebook page, usually on Tuesdays and Thursdays, unless there is an urgent update or essential publication.

Figures 14, 15 and 16 reveal the statistics available by January 2022 for AfriConEU page on Facebook, showing that the page has published 154 posts during this period and is followed/liked by 1.086 users. In terms of engagement, Figure 15 shows that AfriConEU Facebook Page has successfully got 4.958 engagements in its posts⁷.

⁶ <https://www.facebook.com/Africoneu/>

⁷ Facebook’s “Post engagement” is defined as “The number of times that people engaged with your posts through reactions [likes], comments, shares and clicks”. (Facebook, consulted on 28 February 2022)

Figure 13 - AfriConEU Facebook Page

Figure 14 - AfriConEU Facebook Statistics 1, Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

Figure 15 - AfriConEU Facebook Statistics 2, Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

Figure 16 - AfriConEU Facebook Statistics 3, Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

2.2.6.4 Twitter account

The AfriConEU Twitter account⁸ (Figure 17) serves for communication with some of the most significant project's stakeholders, including DIHs and ecosystem builders from both continents, Tech hubs, Business incubators networks, Co-working spaces, Accelerators, Local entrepreneurial and start-up community supporter, SMEs, Pan-African Networks of innovation stakeholders, Public officers/ Policy stakeholders (incl. EU & African), Local governments. Every week (Monday - Wednesday - Friday) three to five tweets are published on the Twitter account and several retweets related to important updates in the project's area. While attending an event or when appropriate, the AfriConEU Twitter account is being used for live updates as well.

Figures 18, 19 and 20 reveal the performance of the project on this social media channel. By January 2022, AfriConEU counted with 556 followers on Twitter, published 31 Tweets, was mentioned 69 times⁹, and stimulated 465 engagements¹⁰.

Figure 17 - AfriConEU Twitter Account

⁸ <https://twitter.com/africoneu/>

⁹ Twitter's "Mention" is defined as "Tweet that contains another person's username anywhere in the body of the Tweet." (Twitter glossary, consulted on 28 February 2022).

¹⁰ Twitter's "Engagement" is defined as "Total number of times a user has interacted with a Tweet. This includes all clicks anywhere on the Tweet (including hashtags, links, avatar, username, and Tweet expansion), retweets, replies, follows, and likes." (Twitter glossary, consulted on 28 February 2022).

Figure 18 - AfriConEU Twitter Statistics 1, Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

Figure 19 - AfriConEU Twitter Statistics 2, Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

Figure 20 - AfriConEU Twitter Statistics 3, Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

2.2.6.5 LinkedIn page

The AfriConEU LinkedIn page¹¹ (Figure 21) serves for communicating with some of the most significant project’s stakeholders, including the same groups targeted with the Twitter account, but also Education and Training organizations. Every week three to five posts are published on the LinkedIn page, usually, on Monday - Wednesday – Friday, unless there is an urgent update or essential publication. In this case, more posts occur during the same days as the scheduled posts.

¹¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/africoneu/>

Figure 21 - AfriConEU LinkedIn page

In Figures 22, 23 and 24, we can consult the performance of AfriConEU on Linked during the first of the project. According the figures, by January 2022, the project has published 278 posts in this social media, and has successfully gathered 1.137 followers and a total of 3.979 pageviews. Concerning the level of engagement, Figure 24 reveals that the project has successfully got 7.482 engagements. These numbers, when compared to the other social media, place LinkedIn as the social media where AfriConEU is better performing, meaning that this social media is most likely to gather the individuals or organisations potentially interested in AfriConEU actions, and, thus, continuous and further investments in this social media are worthy for the next project period.

Figure 22 - AfriConEU LinkedIn Statistics 1, Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

Figure 23 - AfriConEU LinkedIn Statistics 2, Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

Summary	
(for selected time period)	
Total Posts	278
Impressions	96,605
Engagement	7,482
Engagement Rate	7.74%
Clicks	2,677
CTR	2.77%
Likes	4,315
Comments	74
Shares	416

Figure 24 - AfriConEU LinkedIn Statistics 3, Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

2.2.6.6 Instagram account

The AfriConEU Instagram account¹² (Figure 25) serves for more personalized communication with entrepreneurs (focusing on professionals, women, and marginalized youth), Young innovators, ICT professionals, and mentors. Three posts per week are published on Instagram unless there is an urgent update or essential publication. In this case, more posts might occur, either on separate days during the week or the same days as the scheduled posts (Monday - Wednesday - Friday).

Figures 26, 27, 28 and 29 reveals us that, by January 2022, AfriConEU has published 136 posts, was being followed by 623 users and triggered 5.376 engagements.

Figure 25 - AfriConEU Instagram Account

¹² <https://www.instagram.com/africoneu/>

Figure 26 - AfriConEU Instagram Statistics 1, Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

Figure 27 - AfriConEU Instagram Statistics 2, Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

Figure 28 - AfriConEU Instagram Statistics 3, Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

Figure 29 - AfriConEU Instagram Statistics 1, Year 1 (Mar. 2021 – Jan. 2022)

2.2.6.7 YouTube channel

The AfriConEU YouTube channel¹³ (Figure 30) serves to communicate the project to all target audiences, providing simple, friendly, and modern videos.

Apart from short videos with the project's information, more interactive and animated videos will be created and published on the YouTube Channel during the second and third year of the project.

Figure 30 - AfriConEU YouTube Channel

2.2.6.8 Social Media Campaigns in Year 1

To engage more effectively with our followers in social media and provide relevant and target group-oriented content, the following social media campaigns were developed and implemented within the first year of the project (M1-M12):

1. *Suspense* campaign

Once the project's social media accounts were launched, content to attract more followers was created before the release of official information about the project. It was a campaign to spark the curiosity of the growing audience with the aim to anticipate the following updates.

¹³ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC0OPqakH9DrX6li5fAPlrXQ>

The campaign was implemented on all social media.

2. Intro to AfriConEU

After the attraction of followers and the curiosity that the suspense campaign created, a new campaign started, aiming to provide basic information about the project. The information was communicated in a modern, efficient, interactive, and transparent manner through audio-visual material and polls. The basic info included what the project is doing, the vision, the mission, the objectives, the name explanation, the website launch, and the main numbers (project duration, participating partners, countries, and DIHs). The campaign was implemented on all social media.

3. #MeetThePartners

Once the intro was done and the critical information was published on all social media, another campaign took place, intending to introduce the 11 partners of the project one by one. In the context of the campaign, a short bio of each partner and their substantial role in the project was shared. The campaign was implemented on all social media.

4. #Joinus

Entrepreneurs, Digital skills and employment providers, investors, and DIHs were targeted through this campaign to join the project via the website's online application forms. The target groups were motivated to join and gain access to the networking academy built throughout the project's life cycle. The campaign was implemented on all social media. This campaign contributed in the increase of followers by 20% the period that it took place.

5. #AfriConEUpartnerstalk

Through this campaign, the partners shared their concrete objectives for the project. They expressed what they want to achieve in a comprehensive and precise manner accompanied by excellent graphics connected to the project's brand identity. The campaign was implemented on all social media.

Figure 31 – AfriConEU Partners Talk campaign on Instagram

The following social media campaigns have been developed and are being implemented (M2 - Ongoing):

1. #MondayInsights - Instagram

The campaign targets entrepreneurs, professionals, women, marginalized youth, young innovators, ICT professionals, and mentors. During #MondayInsights, insightful information is provided about digital innovation, entrepreneurship, business, and technology. The campaign is being implemented every Monday on Instagram.

2. #WednesdayPolls - LinkedIn

To engage the LinkedIn page's target groups in a participatory and pleasant manner, the campaign creates polls with four or five different answers. The followers choose the answer which suits their preference/ situation. The majority of the polls are related to the project's

area, while to provide a casual environment, the polls sometimes include daily life's topics. The campaign is being implemented every Wednesday on LinkedIn. A total number of 35 polls have been published in Year 1.

3. #FridayMotivation - Instagram

This campaign provides motivational and inspirational quotes from successful entrepreneurs and experts worldwide. All quotes are related to entrepreneurship, business, digital innovation, start-ups, and relevant areas. The campaign is being implemented every Friday on Instagram.

4. #InternationalDays - Facebook

The project raises awareness about international days connected or related to the project's content. The project invites the audience to celebrate each international day's theme through text and visual material. The campaign is being implemented on Facebook.

5. #AfriConEUknowledgepills - Facebook

This campaign includes articles, podcasts, and essential updates in the digital innovation ecosystem, mainly focused on Uganda, Tanzania, Ghana, and Nigeria. The campaign is being implemented on LinkedIn, and some essential pieces are being shared on Facebook.

6. #AfriConEUopportunities - LinkedIn and Twitter

Roundtable discussions, workshops, participation in research, and other opportunities in the project framework are being shared throughout this campaign. It is being implemented mainly on LinkedIn and Twitter.

7. #AfriConEUnews - all social media

#AfriConEUnews provides information about the project, its activities, participation in events, results, published material, press releases, press clips, and general updates on its progress. The campaign is being implemented on all social media.

8. Opportunities and Events – LinkedIn and Twitter

This campaign shares opportunities and events targeting our audience. All the information is provided clearly and comprehensively so that the followers can get the info about the opportunity or event they want just with a few clicks.

9. Newsletter Subscription - LinkedIn, Twitter, and Instagram

This campaign shares regular audience reminders to subscribe to the project's newsletter, issued once every six months. The campaign is being implemented on LinkedIn, Twitter, and Instagram.

10. Job opportunities Tip-offs - LinkedIn

The campaign shares open job opportunities in the four African countries of the project. The users are directed to the project's website, where the job opportunities are concentrated under the Join tab. During the first year of the project, 78 Job opportunities have been published in the section of the website.

2.2.7 Newsletter

Newsletters are sent every six months to inform on the project's activities and progress, retaining the followers and stakeholders' interest. The newsletters are structured based on the following points:

- Introduction: a quick recap of the past six months,
- Upcoming events,
- Interview with someone related to the project whose views can be interesting concerning the project's areas of interest,
- Published deliverables,
- A couple of helpful published articles published on the web (or good practices).

Youthmakers Hub, as the communication and dissemination leading partner, shares the newsletter with the remaining partners, so it can be then shared within their own networks.

A newsletter recipients' list has already been created, through Mailchimp platform, and will be enriched constantly during the project implementation. Data Protection Laws are being fully respected and compliant with the applicable national, European, and international legal framework and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/6798.

During the first year of the project, 500 users have subscribed AfriConEU newsletter.

With the contribution of all partners, Youthmakers Hub has produced [two newsletters](#)¹⁴ during the period M1-M12. The newsletters were circulated in an electronic format to the interested public through the Mailchimp platform, and are also uploaded on the [official project webpage](#).

Figure 32 - Newsletter Visuals

The issues being published illustrate the achievements reached during the reported period, both in terms of project developments as well as peripheral activities, such as participation in external events. Given the importance of the newsletter, it has to be concise and clear without jargon, and include a final text attractive enough to make all kinds of readers want to find out more about the project.

¹⁴ <https://www.africoneu.eu/newsletter/>

Completed AfriConEU Activities

AfriConEU Roundtable discussions: Challenges & Opportunities for EU-Africa Partnerships development

Outbox, from our Consortium, has hosted a series of interactive roundtable discussions. The goal was to highlight the necessity of networking and knowledge sharing, the strengthening of skills, and finding ways to overcome challenges and seize opportunities in the African digital innovation ecosystem.

Coming up: Online Workshop

Workshop: Development of the Trans-Continental Partnerships
We invite you to join us at this participative online workshop hosted by Porto Business School, from our Consortium, aiming to discuss and co-design a programme focused on Africa-Europe partnerships in the innovation ecosystem, particularly among DIHs. The workshop will take place on the 3rd of February 2022 at 10:30 CET. Read more about the event [here](#), or register below.

[Register now](#)

Join the AfriConEU Community of Practice

Do you have an opportunity for our Online Community? Do you have exciting Training Seminars and are looking for participants? Or are you simply looking for an opportunity provided by professionals in the field? Either way, our Online Community of Practice awaits you! You can offer your opportunities [here](#), or easily look for opportunities [here](#).

Participation in Events

AfriConEU at the Emerging Valley | April 7th & 8th, 2021
Our team participated in the Emerging Valley Online Edition. We interacted with the event's speakers, startups, Tech Hubs, and Investors from Africa and Europe, creating networks for potential collaborations in a dynamic and innovative business ecosystem.
→ [Read more](#)

AfriConEU at the AEIP Final Conference | June 29th & 30th, 2021

On 29th and 30th of June 2021, we took part in the Africa-Europe Innovation Partnership's final conference: "Building Sustainable Partnerships with Enrich in Africa & beyond", presenting the project. In addition, we connected with similar initiatives and discussed future synergies. → [Read more](#)

AfriConEU in the Press

During the last months, the development of the project has gained even more international recognition from several media related to innovation and entrepreneurship both in Africa and in Europe, including Tech Nova, Ameyaw Debrah, and startup.gr among others. See AfriConEU in the media.

Figure 33 – Newsletter Campaign Visuals

Table 3 - List of Newsletters Issues

Newsletter issue	Reviewer	Date for the newsletter to be sent to reviewer	Date for the newsletter to be sent	Number of recipients
#1 (July 2021)	INOVA+	5th July 2021	16th July 2021	230
#2 (February 2022)	ECA	17th February 2022	21st February 2022	502

2.2.8 Leaflet

A project leaflet was developed with key points about the project and relevant information, targeting the main audiences and general public (Figure 34). Apart from the English version, it translated into Greek, Italian, Portuguese, and Slovenian (AfriConEU partners' official languages). Available in two formats, one for digital use and one printed for use at events and face-to-face distribution.

Figure 34 - AfriConEU Leaflet

2.2.9 Videos

The project is developing promotional videos for AfriConEU, which are then shared on the YouTube Channel and all social media. Two videos have been developed in Year 1, both are teasers for the project including main aim, objectives, activities and consortium partners.

2.2.10 Press Releases

Press releases are written and published every four months, including updates regarding the project’s activities and progress. Written in English, partners have been translating them into their language and sharing them through their national media channels. The two press releases of Year 1 have been published in 7 websites; all publications can be found in the section [in the media](#) of the website.

Figure 35 - AfriConEU Publication of Press Releases

2.3 Dissemination activities

2.3.1 Presentation of the project at third-party events

The AfriConEU project and partners have been participating in local, national, and international conferences, acting as “AfriConEU ambassadors”.

Table 4 and Table 4 provides a list of indicative relevant events which are suggested to all partners to attend as they are all relevant to AfriConEU project.

Table 4 - List of AfriConEU relevant events & conferences Year 1

Month	Title	Location	Date
March	Driving Business in Africa	Online	16 March 2021
	The Future of Work in Africa	Online	16 March 2021
	IoT Forum Africa 2021	Online	25-26 March 2021

April	Emerging Valley	Online	07-08 April 2021
May	Digitalizing Africa	Online	04 May 2021
	Africa Tech Week	Online	05-06 May 2021
	Afrobytes	Online	25 May 2021
June	Women Tech Global Conference	Online	07 June 2021
	Africa Trade and Investment Convention	Amsterdam, Netherlands	11-12 June 2021
	Viva Technology	Paris, France & Online	16-19 June 2021
	Dublin Tech Summit	Online	17 June 2021
	9th Digital Africa Conference	Online	22 June 2021
	European Research & Innovation Days	Online	23-24 th June 2021
August	sSTARTUp Day 2021	Tartu, Estonia & Online	25-27 August 2021
September	Growth Marketing Summit 2021	Frankfurt, Germany	02 September 2021
	Africa Tech Summit	Nairobi, Kenya	14-15 September 2021
	SA Innovation Summit	Cape Town, South Africa & Online	21-23 September 2021
October	IoT Solutions World Congress	Barcelona, Spain	05 - 07 October 2021
November	Africa Tech	Cape Town, South Africa & Online	08 - 12 November 2021
	Global Entrepreneurship Congress	Online	14-17 November 2021
	IoT Tech Expo Europe 2021	Amsterdam, Netherlands	23-24 November 2021
December	EU - Africa Business Summit	Marrakech, Morocco	29-30 November 2021

Table 5 - List of upcoming events & conferences relevant for AfriConEU, 2022

Month	Title	Location	Date
February	Plastic waste management in Africa	Online	5th Feb 2022
	UK - Africa Technology & Innovation Summit	Online	17 feb 2022, 12:30 – 17:00 (UTC +02:00)
	African Digital Week 2022 - Virtual Events & Expo	Online	21st - 26th Feb 2022
	23rd Edition - CFO Leadership Summit: Africa	Online	23rd Feb 2022 11:00 AM-04:00 PM (UTC +3:00)
March	3rd ANNUAL AFRICA IMPACT INVESTING & SUSTAINABLE FINANCE SUMMIT 2022	Online	24th March, 2022

	Food & Beverage Networking Africa Q1 2022	Online	31 Mar 2022
April	5th Africa Agri Expo - Virtual Connect 2022	Online	13 Apr 2022, - 14 Apr 2022
	Mining & Metals Networking Africa Q2 2022	Online	28th Apr 2022
May	Energy Networking Africa Q2 2022	Online	26th May 2022
June	Construction & Infrastructure Networking Africa Q2 2022	Online	30th Jun 2022
October	IoT Solutions World Congress	Barcelona, Spain	05 - 07 October 2022

2.3.2 Synergies with relevant initiatives, networks, and projects

Developing synergies and networking with relevant initiatives is one of the project’s priorities. Such actions enable AfriConEU to reach different target audiences more effectively. The initial plan to target relevant industries and networks included the following initiatives:

- [AfriLabs](#)
- [The Africa-Europe Innovation Partnership](#): AfriConEU members participated in the Final Conference of the Africa-Europe Innovation Partnership.
- [DIHNET](#)
- [AUEU Youth Cooperation Hub](#): The Dissemination Manager of AfriConEU is a member of this network and represented the project during the Africa Europe week 2022 in Brussels.
- [DISRUPT AFRICA](#)

AfriConEU will strengthen the broader Africa-Europe partnership, developing the connections of the local players with the existing consortium networks. Ultimately, this action will connect the project formally with the key players in Africa’s and Europe’s digital innovation scenes.

2.3.3 ICT-58 Family projects

AfriConEU (coordinated by INOVA+) has successfully initiated the so-called “*ICT-58 Family meetings*”, which gather the projects funded within ICT-58, with the aim of stimulating and strengthening the exchange of knowledge, experiences and the creation of synergies. In Year 1, two meetings took place, in June and September with AFriConEU, [DIGILOGIC](#) and

[HUBiquitous](#) projects. A third meeting is already scheduled to March 2022 and will count with the participation of the recent projects approved under the ICT-58 topic, namely [D4DHub](#) and [AEDIB|NET](#).

Figure 36 - ICT-58 Family projects meeting

2.3.4 Display AfriConEU on partners' institutional website

Each partner has been requested to write a text about the AfriConEU project and include it on their website (and share it on their social media).

Figure 37 – Display of AfriConEU in partners' websites

3. Actions expected from the partners

All partners are expected to contribute to the communication and dissemination efforts. Most of the activities planned for Year 2 and 3 have been outlined in the previous pages. In this section, we intend to address the work distribution among the partners.

3.1. Using project image and disclaimer

All actions should refer to or include:

- The project's common visual identity: logo and standard manual (the needed files are available in the project shared folder, on Microsoft Teams).
- The project Url: <https://africoneu.eu/>.
- Acknowledgement of EU public funding: *"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016687."*
- The official EU logo (EU emblem can be found [here](#). The guidelines on how to use it can be found [here¹⁵](#)).

3.2. Stakeholder's database

Whenever partners make new contacts and links with networks interested in being part of the project, they should fill/update in a database (.xls) that was created for that purpose and which is available in the project shared folder, on Microsoft Teams.

3.3. Contribution to the newsletter

The partners are invited to contribute to the newsletter content depending on the project's ongoing activities and tasks. They are expected to send relevant material to Youthmakers Hub to be published in the Newsletter, ideally two weeks before the launch date. This will help plan so that everything can be reviewed and placed into a proper template before sending it out. Youthmakers Hub will send the Newsletter to the contacts in the project database. All

¹⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/use-emblem_en.pdf

partners are expected to send it to their contacts. The partners are kindly requested to send proof of this to Youthmakers Hub.

3.4 Partners' social media accounts

The partners are advised to post on their social media accounts whenever essential news on the project or a relevant milestone has been reached. They are expected to share the project's press releases, videos, good practices, newsletters or deliverables. Also, they are expected to share any news about the project on local media. They are also encouraged to share articles on topics they consider to be related to the project. They are also highly encouraged to tag relevant partners and the AfriConEU social media accounts. All partners' social media accounts can be found in Annex 2.

3.5 Press releases and media contacts

The partners are expected to translate press releases to their language (when needed) and send them to their contacts in the media. Proof of this should be sent to Youthmakers Hub. Partners are also encouraged to write their own press releases, including the mandatory elements - AfriConEU logo, website, and the acknowledgement of EU funding. They are also expected to share any media features or articles on their social media accounts and send them to Youthmakers Hub for press clipping or adding them in a file shared in the Microsoft Teams folder. Moreover, press releases published in the media (*clipping*) are being displayed also at the respective section of the [website](https://www.africoneu.eu/in-the-media/)¹⁶. For Year 2, three press releases will be published (April 2022, August 2022, and December 2022)

3.6 Events

For each event that partners organize or attend, they should use the project's visual materials (i.e., leaflets) and branding (project logo, colour palette, and fonts). The events should be announced on the partners' website and social media (the partners should remember to tag

¹⁶ <https://www.africoneu.eu/in-the-media/>

@africoneu). Whenever possible/appropriate, the partners are encouraged to tweet during the event they are attending and communicate with Youthmakers Hub to send relevant information to be published from the AfriConEU Twitter account. A template has been created to report events (it can be found in the Microsoft Teams folder) and at the end of this document in Annex 2. The partners should send the event report to Youthmakers Hub within two weeks after completing the event, accompanied by at least two pictures of high quality. There is also a file where the partners can list the events they are planning to attend in the Microsoft Teams folder. All events are being uploaded on the project website under the section [What's New](#).

4. Impact Measurement

The communication and dissemination efforts support the overall goals of the project. There are specific goals and objectives to be achieved for AfriConEU. Communication and dissemination activities should help achieve these goals, with particular attention given to Digital Innovation Hubs and Entrepreneurs' involvement. Therefore, metrics and indicators were developed for the communication activities as presented in Table 6.

Table 6 - Communication & Dissemination Key Performance Indicators

Tool Channels	KPIs	Expected Results	Indicators Year 1
AfriConEU Website	Number of visits	1000 visits per month.	1.100/ month
	Time spent on the web platform	> 40% of visitors spending 1 minute or more in the platform	60%
	Returning visitors	More than 40% of returning visitors	52.66 %
Communication material	Number of items distributed	At least 1500 flyers distributed	No physical events yet
	Number of contacts from stakeholders	At least 100 contacts showing interest in receiving AfriConEU promotion materials	250 / M12
Social media	Number of members and engagement	LinkedIn: At least 200 followers	1.137 / M12
		YouTube: at least 100 subscribers	38 / M12
		Twitter: 500 followers by end of M12 / 1000 followers by end of M28	593 / M12
		Instagram: 500 followers by end of M12 / 1000 followers by end of M28	623 / M12
		Facebook: 200 followers by end of M12 / 500 followers by end of M28	1.094 / M12
		More than 40% of posts are shared	45%
Press releases	Press list	1 press list with at least quarterly updates and press contacts from the African and European titles from the countries represented in the Consortium	Done
	Number of press releases issued	At least 3 press releases issued by the project per year	3 / M12
	Clipping/publications coverage	At least 10 press clippings (articles) per year	10 / M12
	Media Interviews	At least 2 interviews per year	2/ M12
Newsletters	Number of subscribers	500 by end of M12 / 1000 by end of M24 / 1500 by end of M36	502 / M12
	Number of Newsletter issues	6 newsletter issues throughout the project's lifecycle	2 / M12
	Opening rate per newsletter	Average of at least 18% opening rate by end of M12/ 20% by end of M24 / 25% by end of M36	66,4% / M12

5. Planning

Table 7 presents the activities planned for the period M13- M24 of the project in what concerns the development of communication tools and the production of deliverables within WP6.

Table 7 - Planning Year 2

Activity	Deadline	Partner	Notes
D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan – Second version	February 2022	YMH	It will be delivered 28 th February 2022
Press Release 4	April 2022	YMH	It will be delivered 20 th April 2022
Newsletter 3	July 2022	YMH	It will be delivered 15 th July 2022
Press Release 5	August 2022	YMH	It will be delivered 20 th August 2022
Press Release 6	December 2022	YMH	It will be delivered 20 th December 2022
Newsletter	January 2023	YMH	It will be delivered 15 th January 2023

6. Conclusion

In light of the above, the communication and dissemination activities during the first year of AfriConEU were completed as planned. All efforts have contributed to creating awareness around the project and have enabled AfriConEU to reach the target groups identified for the project. During the reporting period, those actions aimed at adjusting the communication actions. Moreover, social media actions for each target group have been developed, and the WP leader plans to continue improving these strategies in the coming months. Finally, as detailed in the section 4 - *Impact measurement*, the dissemination and communication activities of the consortium have overall far exceeded the measurement goals set at the onset of the project.

In the upcoming year, the consortium will continue promoting the outputs of the project to ensure the widest possible reach and adoption of the AfriConEU. Accordingly, the strategy has been tailored to contribute to the main objective of the project: to become the first Trans-continental Networking academy for African and European Digital Innovation Hubs. It follows, then, that the complexity of communication activities will increase as the project evolves, especially when considering the new stage in which the Capacity Building programme will be developed. Also, AfriConEU needs to expand its external network, and the project's results need to be disseminated. The updating of the communication strategy will be a tool for the project's continued development.

Annex 1: Template for Reporting Events

- This template should be sent to Youthmakers Hub by partners after attending/organizing/speaking at any event so dissemination efforts can be tracked
- Still, it is advisable to inform us in advance whenever you are attending an event to promote it on our website and social media channels.
- Please, take at least two pictures of the event to display the information on our website.

This template can be found in the MS folder [here](#).

Template for Reporting Events

Title of the event	
Date	DD/MM/YYYY
Location	City, Country
Partner attending	
Description	Include information on type of event, objectives, scope, structure and organizers – as applicable
Type of participation	Organizer / Speaker / Attendant
Main Audience	DIHs, Entrepreneurs, Investors, Policymakers, others
Results/ Outcome	What is the impact of the event on the project? Did it create awareness, encourage involvement, create synergies, strengthen links with public bodies, consolidate exploitation?
Documents or links for further information	Agenda, web, presentation etc.
Link in MS folder with photos	(Upload photos from the event in the shared MS folder, create your own folder for each event here)
Other Comments	

Annex 2: Partners' Communication Channels and Contacts

INOVA+ Innovation Services S.A.

Website	https://inova.business/
Twitter	-
LinkedIn	INOVA+
Facebook	-
Instagram	-
YouTube channel	INOVA SA
Contact person	Ana Solange Leal
Contact e-mail	ana.leal@inova.business

Emerging Communities Africa

Website	https://www.emergingcommunities.africa
Twitter	@emergingtechAF
LinkedIn	Emerging Communities Africa
Facebook	@emergingtechaf
Instagram	emergingtechaf
YouTube channel	Emerging Communities Africa
Contact person	Peace Odili
Contact e-mail	peace.odili@emergingcommunities.africa

Youthmakers Hub

Website	www.youthmakershub.com
Twitter	@youthmakershub
LinkedIn	Youthmakers Hub
Facebook	@youthmakershub
Instagram	youthmkarershub
YouTube channel	Youthmakers Hub
Contact person	Marilena Maragkou
Contact e-mail	info@youthmakershub.com

ASSOCIACAO PORTO BUSINESS SCHOOL (PBS)- U. PORTO

Website	https://www.pbs.up.pt/
Twitter	-
LinkedIn	Porto Business School
Facebook	@portobusinessschool
Instagram	portobusinessschool
YouTube channel	Porto Business School
Contact person	Catarina Reis
Contact e-mail	creis@pbs.up.pt

OUTBOX (U) LIMITED

Website	http://www.outbox.co.ug/
Twitter	Outbox
LinkedIn	Outbox Uganda
Facebook	@OutboxHub
Instagram	outboxhub
YouTube channel	Outbox
Contact person	Perez Apiyo Masinde
Contact e-mail	pmasinde@outbox.co.ug

DPIXEL SRL

Website	https://dpixel.it/
Twitter	@dpixel_vc
LinkedIn	dPixel
Facebook	@dpixelvc
Instagram	-
YouTube channel	-
Contact person	Damelio Lorenzo
Contact e-mail	dameliolorenzo@gmail.com

Stimmuli for Social Change

Website	http://www.stimmuli.eu/
Twitter	@StimmuliFChange
LinkedIn	Stimmuli For Social Change
Facebook	@Stimmuli
Instagram	-
YouTube channel	-
Contact person	Irene Kalemaki
Contact e-mail	irene.kalemaki@stimmuli.eu

ITC - Innovation Technology Cluster Murska Sobota

Website	http://www.itc-cluster.com/
Twitter	@ITC_cluster
LinkedIn	ITC - Innovation Technology Cluster
Facebook	-
Instagram	-
YouTube channel	-
Contact person	Sasa Straus
Contact e-mail	sasa.straus@itc-cluster.com

Buni Innovation Hub

Website	www.bunihub.or.tz
Twitter	@bunihub
LinkedIn	Buni Hub
Facebook	@bunihub
Instagram	bunihub
YouTube channel	Buni Hub
Contact person	Edwin Bakalemwa
Contact e-mail	edwin.bakalemwa@costech.or.tz

Africa Technology Business Network

Website	www.africatbn.com
Twitter	@africatbn
LinkedIn	ATBN
Facebook	@AfricaTBN
Instagram	
YouTube channel	
Contact person	Eunice Baguma Ball
Contact e-mail	eunice@africatbn.com

Hapa Foundation

Website	www.hapaspace.com
Twitter	@hapaSpace
LinkedIn	hapaSpace Collaborative Hub
Facebook	@hapaspace
Instagram	hapaspace
YouTube channel	hapa Space
Contact person	Gideon Brefo
Contact e-mail	gideon@hapaspace.com